

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 144

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 144

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 144:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 144:1 לְדָוִד אֲבִירֹדֵי יְהוָה אֲצִוֶּהִי</p>
<p>Psa. 144:1 Blessed be the LORD, ^amy rock,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Who ^btrains my hands for war, <i>And</i> my fingers for battle;</p> <p>² My lovingkindness and ^amy fortress,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">My ^bstronghold and my deliverer, My ^cshield and He in whom I take refuge,</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Who ^dsubdues ¹my people under me.</p> <p>³ O LORD, ^awhat is man, that You take knowledge of him? Or the son of man, that You think of him?</p> <p>⁴ ^aMan is like a mere breath; His ^bdays are like a passing shadow.</p> <p>Psa. 144:5 ^aBow Your heavens, O LORD, and ^bcome down; ^aTouch the mountains, that they may smoke.</p> <p>⁶ Flash forth ^alightning and scatter them;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Send out Your ^barrows and confuse them.</p> <p>⁷ Stretch forth Your hand ^afrom on high;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Rescue me and ^bdeliver me out of great waters, Out of the hand of ^caliens</p> <p>⁸ Whose mouths ^aspeak deceit,</p>	<p>הַמִּלְמַד יָדַי לְקָרֵב אֲצַבְעוֹתַי לְמִלְחָמָה: ²</p> <p>חֲסִדַי וּמְצֻדָתַי מִשְׁנֵבֵי וּמִפְלִטֵי לִי מִגְּנִי וּבֹרֵחֵי חֲסִיתִי הַרְוֹדֵד עִמִּי תַחְתֵּי: ³ יְהוָה מִה־אֲדָם וַתִּדְעֵהוּ בֶן־אָנוּשׁ וַתַּחֲשֹׁבֵהוּ: ⁴ אֲדָם לְהִקְבֹּל דָּמָה יָמָיו כְּצֶלַע עֹבֵר: ⁵ יְהוָה חֵט־שָׁמַיִךְ וַתִּהְרַד גַּע בְּהַרִים וַיִּעַשְׂנוּ: ⁶ בְּרוּךְ בְּרוּךְ וַתִּפְיֹצֵם שְׁלַח חֲצִיֶיךָ וַתַּהַמֵּם: ⁷ שְׁלַח יָדְךָ מִמְרוֹם פְּצַנִּי וְהַצִּילֵנִי מִיַּד רַבִּים מִיַּד בְּנֵי נֹכֵר: ⁸ אֲשֶׁר בִּיהֵם דְּבַר־שְׁוֹא וַיִּמְיֵן יָמִין שִׁקְרָ: ⁹ אֱלֹהִים שִׁיר חֲדָשׁ אֲשִׁירָה לְךָ בְּגִבְלֵי עֲשׂוֹר אֲזַמְרָה־לְךָ: ¹⁰ תְּנוֹתֵן תְּשׁוּעָה לְמַלְכִים הַפּוֹצֵה אֶת־דָּוִד עַבְדּוֹ מִתַּרְבֵּי רָעָה: ¹¹ פְּצַנִּי וְהַצִּילֵנִי מִיַּד בְּנֵי־נֹכֵר אֲשֶׁר בִּיהֵם דְּבַר־שְׁוֹא וַיִּמְיֵן יָמִין שִׁקְרָ: ¹² אֲשֶׁר בְּנִינוּ וּבְנֵי־עַמִּים מְגִדְלִים בְּנִעוּרֵיהֶם בְּנוֹתֵינוּ כְּזֹרֵת מִחֲטָבוֹת תְּבַנִּית הֵיכַל: ¹³ מִזִּוְיָנוּ מִלְּאִים מִפִּיקִים מִזֶּן אֱלֹהִים צִוּנוּנוּ מֵאֲלִיפוֹת מִרְבָּבוֹת בְּחוֹצוֹתֵינוּ: ¹⁴ אֱלֹהֵינוּ מִסְּפָלִים אֵין־פֶּרֶץ וְאֵין יוֹצֵאת וְאֵין צֹחֶה בְּרַחֲבֵתֵינוּ: ¹⁵ אֲשֶׁר־יִהְיֶה הָעַם שִׁפְכָה לֹא אֲשֶׁר־יִהְיֶה הָעַם שִׁיחֲנָה אֱלֹהֵיו:</p>

And whose ^bright hand is a right hand of falsehood.

Psa. 144:9 I will sing a ^anew song to You, O God;

Upon a ^bharp of ten strings I will sing praises to You,

¹⁰ Who ^agives salvation to kings,
Who ^brescues David His servant from the evil sword.

¹¹ Rescue me and deliver me out of the hand of ^aaliens,

Whose mouth ^bspeaks deceit

And whose ^cright hand is a right hand of falsehood.

Psa. 144:12 Let our sons in their youth be as ^agrown-up plants,

And our daughters as ^bcorner pillars ¹fashioned as for a palace;

¹³ Let our ^agranaries be full, furnishing every kind of produce,

And our flocks bring forth thousands and ten thousands in our ¹fields;

¹⁴ Let our ^acattle ¹bear
Without ^{2b}mishap and without ³loss,

Let there be no ^doutcry in our streets!

¹⁵ How blessed are the people who are so situated;

How ^ablessed are the people whose God is the LORD!

References

Psalm 144:1

^aPs 18:2

^b2 Sam 22:35; Ps 18:34

Psalm 144:2

¹Another reading is *peoples*

^aPs 18:2; 91:2

^bPs 59:9

^cPs 3:3; 28:7; 84:9

^dPs 18:39

Psalm 144:3

^aJob 7:17; Ps 8:4; Heb 2:6

Psalm 144:4

^aPs 39:11

^bJob 8:9; 14:2; Ps 102:11; 109:23

Psalm 144:5

^aPs 18:9

^bIs 64:1

^cPs 104:32

Psalm 144:6

^aPs 18:14

^bPs 7:13; 58:7; Hab 3:11; Zech 9:14

Psalm 144:7

^aPs 18:16

^bPs 69:1, 14

^cPs 18:44; 54:3

Psalm 144:8

^aPs 12:2; 41:6

^bGen 14:22; Deut 32:40; Ps 106:26; Is 44:20

Psalm 144:9

^aPs 33:3; 40:3

^bPs 33:2

Psalm 144:10

^aPs 18:50

^b2 Sam 18:7; Ps 140:7

Psalm 144:11

^aPs 18:44; 54:3

^bPs 12:2; 41:6

^cGen 14:22; Deut 32:40; Ps 106:26; Is 44:20

Psalm 144:12

¹Lit *cut after the pattern of*

^aPs 92:12-14; 128:3

^bSong 4:4; 7:4

Psalm 144:13

¹Lit *outside*

^aProv 3:9, 10

Psalm 144:14

¹Lit *be laden*

²Lit *bursting forth*

³Lit *going out*

^aProv 14:4

^b2 Kin 25:10, 11

^cAmos 5:3

^dIs 24:11; Jer 14:2

Psalm 144:15

^aPs 33:12

Targum

Psa. 144:1 Composed by David. Blessed is the LORD, my strength, who instructs my hands for battle, my fingers to wage war. ² He who acts favorably, and my mighty fortress; my strength, and the one who delivers me; my shield, and I have hoped in his word; he who tramples the Gentiles under me. ³ O LORD, what is a son of man, that you know him? The sons of men, that you think of him? ⁴ A son of man is likened to nothing; his days are like a shadow that passes. ⁵ O LORD, bend the heavens and be revealed; touch the mountains, and they send up smoke. ⁶ Make lightning flash, and scatter them; send arrows and confound them. ⁷ Extend your hand from highest heaven; deliver me and save me from the hordes that are likened to many waters, from the hand of the sons of foreigners. ⁸ Whose mouth speaks vain oaths, and their Torah is a Torah of deceit. ⁹ God, I will sing a new psalm in your presence; with the lyre of ten strings I will make music in your presence. ¹⁰ Who gives redemption to kings, who delivers David his servant from the wicked sword of Goliath. ¹¹ Deliver me and save me from the hands of the sons of foreigners, whose mouth speaks vain oaths, and their Torah is a Torah of deceit. ¹² For our sons are like plantings of date-palms, growing in the learning of Torah from their youth; our daughters are beautiful and fit for priests who serve within the temple. ¹³ Our treasuries are full, supplying needs from year to year; our flocks are bearing thousands, they increase by tens of thousands in our streets. ¹⁴ Our oxen bear great loads; there is no harshness and no expression of evil; there is no clamor of weeping in our squares. ¹⁵ Happy the people for whom it is thus; happy the people whose God is the LORD.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This is a Psalm composed by David. It is a Psalm of thanksgiving and praise at the beginning of his reign after the LORD granted him victory over his enemies. In the Psalm, David expressed the Jewish attitude toward war and warriors. The triumphant soldier has no claim to success, for he is only a tool in the LORD's hands.

Notes on this Psalm

Do you praise the LORD if things are going well in your life? Numerous times people take the LORD for granted until something terrible happens. Then they go to their place of worship and plead with the LORD for help. People must remember that the good things in their lives come from the LORD. The bad things are usually caused by freewill or the influence of Evil Inclination. Prayer should comprise praising the LORD for the triumphant of life and for help when bad things happen.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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